

Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan

FRESH-D7.2-CommunicationDisseminationPlan

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Version control sheet

WP	7. Communication and Dissemination
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1. Executive summary

This deliverable aims to present the dissemination and communication plan as well as the associated actions that will be implemented during the FRESH project. The strategy is integrated under WP7 – Communication and Dissemination. The leader of WP7 (CNR) will be responsible for the overall management and support of the activities defined under the present dissemination and communication plan and will develop the main tools and materials to be used during the project. All partners will also be actively involved in the dissemination and communication actions and are highly committed to ensure a satisfactory dissemination of project results. In general, the expected contribution from partners is to:

- Implement promotional and dissemination campaigns in their own countries and at European level;
- Exploit their contacts and networks;
- Supply news and updates for the web portal and news;
- Interact with the project posts on various Social Media Channels;
- Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes;

The present document outlines:

- The objectives of the strategy;
- The main target audiences and respective dissemination and communication objectives;
- FRESH brand identity;
- The main dissemination and communication tools and channels to reach the audiences;
- The main activities including an indicative timeline for their implementation;
- Conclusions, outlining the dissemination and communication assets and role of the project.

A number of activities have already been completed such as the Website and social media platforms. Others are coming online as will be explained in this document.

2. Objectives of the plan

The main objective of the dissemination and communication plan of the FRESH project is to offer partners a set of guidelines, responsibilities and timelines on how/when/where to disseminate the project, as well as to encourage them to use their channels (corporate websites, social networks, etc) to support the dissemination, with the main goal of gathering the ideal conditions to. As set out in the Grant Agreement (as follows). Some of the activities have already been achieved (marked in red) while others will be coming online in the next period.

Task 7.1: Initial Plan for the Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (M1-M12; ICCOM and all partners. This task will cover the planning of the communication actions of FRESH project. Different communication channels, such as multimedia, internet, social media, press and specialised magazines will be used to gain visibility and increase interest on project results. The communication activities will be run continuously throughout the project in order to promote the exchange of information between the project and the related communities. New technologies and their benefits will be made widely known to related industries and potential customers by implementing efficient communication measures. The main initial communication activities will include:

- *Project identity, presentation and document templates.*
- *Initial poster presentation and brochure about FRESH project goals and consortium.*
- *Creation Project Website.*
- *Creation of multiple accounts in social media (including LinkedIn, Twitter and Research Gate among others).*
- *Press release by all partners*
- *Communication Plan for the FRESH* The outputs of this Task 7.1, in terms of communication and dissemination activities, will be the website of the project (D7.1) and the initial communication and dissemination plan (D7.2).

3. The strategy

The strategy focuses on establishing and executing a realistic dissemination and communication plan in line with the progress of the project and the utilization of appropriate tools, channels and actions to communicate with the target audiences in a defined timeline. To achieve dissemination and communication objectives in a timely and adequate manner, the FRESH consortium will follow the roadmap below:

- Planning of Activities (M1 – M6): Identify the communication and dissemination strategy and plan to ensure the best impact of project outcomes.
- Implementation Phase (M6 – M24): Produce a comprehensive set of tools (supports and channels) to diffuse key messages extracted from the project results to the identified targeted groups.
- Monitoring Activities (M6 – M24): Carefully analyze and assess the impact and success of dissemination activities.
- Sustainability (M24 – M36): Identify and establish mechanisms needed to ensure persistent and long-lasting visibility of FRESH outcomes.

4. Target audience, dissemination and communication objectives

The main goal of all Dissemination and Communication activities is to maximize the exploitation potential of the knowledge and results deriving from the FRESH project. To this end, the first step of the plan consists of identifying the groups of stakeholders that can benefit from the achievements of the FRESH project and the most relevant channels to reach each group. Table 1 summarizes the target stakeholder groups, the key messages to share, the communication channels and the channels that will be used.

Table 1: Stakeholder target groups.

	Stakeholder group	Key message	DIS-COM activities	DIS-COM channel
Primary target group	Renewable Energy storage sector. Industrial producers of CO ₂ emissions. All industrial stakeholders in CO ₂ conversion technology. Producers of fuel cell/electrolysis components and materials.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical properties of materials, components and systems • Costs and manufacturing processes • Parameter validation and efficiency increase potential • Requirements on high performance 	Presentations, handouts, website, social media posts, scientific publications	National and European industry associations, magazines/website, social media, workshops, symposium, conferences and relevant exhibitions
Secondary target group	Users and customers of similar material in another technological context such as mobility, aerospace, filter technology, hydraulic sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show the contribution of the expected material properties to other processes • Material validation 	Presentations, handouts, website, social media posts, scientific publications	Direct contact by partners, workshops and conferences, industry fairs and relevant exhibitions
Tertiary target group	Researchers	Demonstrate the achieved results and share new knowledge generated	Presentations, scientific publications	Scientific conferences, scientific journals magazines
	Policy makers, regulators and international organisations	Technology advancements and role of legislation and standards to support market uptake	Presentations in committees and workshop	Committee meetings, magazines, web site, personal communication by mail
	General public and citizens	Information about the project and future perspectives for a green hydrogen economy	Website post, magazine articles, social media post, presentations	Website, social media, workshops, magazines

DIS-COM activities will be performed constantly during the project. A detailed schedule will be planned on a yearly basis in order to ensure maximization of the reach, effectiveness, extensibility, and sustainability of the project results. In fact, the main characteristics guiding the design of the DIS-COM Plan will be:

- Reach: reaching the target groups in Europe and possibly all over the world;
- Effectiveness: using effective tools, methods and language for communicating with the targeted stakeholder groups;
- Extensibility: allowing the DIS-COM tools wide diffusion in terms of geographical area coverage and size of the involved stakeholders;
- Sustainability: making the communication and dissemination infrastructure to function long after the completion of the project.

In support for these issues three important principles will be taken into account:

- 1) All of the project outcomes are elements for communication and dissemination material (in line with the IPR conditions agreed by the partners and with the principles of the Data Management Plan);
- 2) Communication and dissemination actions are ongoing activities for the entire duration of the project;
- 3) All the beneficiaries are involved and take part in the DIS-COM activities, as promoters of a specific action or as contributors to the initiative proposed inside the WP7 by other partners;

All the relevant products and processes developed as intermediate results during the project life-cycle will be considered for DIS-COM activities. Intermediary results play a key role in contributing to achieve the final objectives and impact, and therefore are relevant content for communication and dissemination actions independently from the final outputs of the project. However, some outputs may not be suitable for dissemination, either because they are intended for partners' use only or because their content makes them inappropriate for dissemination. Results and information will be carefully analyzed before dissemination through the selected DIS-COM channels.

5. Exploitable Knowledge

An important issue when designing the DIS-COM plan is to understand from the beginning the type of output that will result from the project. To this end, the project outputs will be classified in two main types:

- Knowledge, know-how and experience: this type of result is suitable for dissemination to the scientific community through scientific publications, conference presentations as well as to professional stakeholders that might be interested in best practices and experience gathered from the demonstration activities during the project. All the project management and communication solutions fit this category.
- Hard Outputs: this type of results consists of the technological components and/or the full FRESH system that will be of interest to industrial stakeholders in the energy sector, as well as to SMEs and companies operating in the field of fuel cell technologies.

Figure 1 shows the planned timeline regarding the DIS-COM and exploitation activities. In comparison with the main WP7 milestones and objectives as planned in the Grant Agreement, DIS-COM activities are timely characterized by different phases that could be summarized in two main processes:

- The INFORMATION process is characterized by the use of unidirectional communication channels to increase visibility of the project and awareness of the stakeholders and EU society on the FRESH topics;
- The DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION process is characterized by the use of bidirectional communication channels that allows the interaction with the targeted stakeholders and a more effective action to collect interest for the exploitation of the project results.

Figure 1. Communication Plan

At the end of the project, the DIS-COM activities will converge to the main communication channel (i.e. the website) that will remain open after the end of the project. The website will be updated by CNR at least for the next 12 months after the end of the project. Additional press releases and scientific publication could be published by each partner in order to disseminate the final results also after the project completion planned at M36.

6. Deliverables, communication rules and agreements

It is worth recalling that the EC definition of dissemination is “the disclosure of knowledge by any appropriate means other than publication resulting from the formalities for protecting knowledge”. This obligation is qualified by highlighting the importance of ensuring that dissemination does not adversely affect the protection or use of the knowledge generated and, in all cases, dissemination must safeguard Intellectual Property Rights, confidentiality, and the legitimate interests of the parties.

The deliverables that are prepared as documents during the duration of the project must be considered as knowledge of the project and therefore the right to use them needs to be clearly defined for all participants. The issue of ownership of the written reports/documents are addressed herein.

Under copyright law, the author or authors of a work must agree to the copying and dissemination of the work. An important point to note is that the protected work itself may be used without permission as long as this use does not involve copying or dissemination. Therefore, the same access rights as applied to other pre-existing know-how and knowledge within this project also apply to written deliverables and reports that a participant intends to copy or disseminate outside the project.

Deliverables within the project have pre-defined dissemination categories (see GA):

- PU: Public (without restriction, therefore available to all for communication, dissemination and use);
- PP: restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services);
- RE: restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services);
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).

These categories ensure that the Intellectual Property Rights referenced within the Deliverables are protected pending adequate IPR protection and/or that the know-how or trade secrets or other confidential information referenced therein are guaranteed inside the consortium until a final common IP agreement is defined. It is important to note that Confidential Information or information that may be eligible for IP protection cannot regain the confidential status nor the right to IP protection once disclosed publicly.

7. Geographical dimension and level of engagement

The communication and dissemination activities will be performed considering different geographical dimensions.

- International Level: The project results are relevant to the international community operating in renewable energy production and storage, CO₂ capture and transformation. It must be noted, though, that although the interest in the topic can be considered global, one of the barriers refers specifically to the difficulty of bridging the national regulatory differences for the implementation of such technologies.
- European Level: it is the most significant level for the project DIS-COM activities. One very practical reason for this is that the majority of organizations involved in the projects are European organizations and have therefore an interest in this geographical dimension. From a more general point of view it is also to be considered that the seasonal storage of renewable energy is now on the forefront of many countries' agenda and therefore the theme of the project can be considered relevant for organizations and institutions on a very large scale.
- National (and Regional) Level: it is essential that project partners carry out dissemination activities in their own countries and within their reach of influence in order to secure national support on different levels with a medium to long term perspective of implementing the FRESH results;
- Personal Level: All key personnel who are directly affiliated with the FRESH project in the partner institutions are encouraged and expected to put personal effort to promote awareness, understanding and utilization of the project outcomes through individual networking resources.

8. Communication Plan

Communication actions will be performed using different communication channels and tools according to the type of stakeholder target group and the desired engagement level. The first six months of the project have been focused on developing and setting up the tools and channels that will be used for the communication activities during the entire project. Special attention has been paid to developing the visual identity, the website, the social media and the infographics that will distinguish the FRESH project. The channels will be constantly updated with news on the project (website and social media) whereas the tools will be flexibly used as building blocks for designing further communication materials (e.g. the graphics will be used in posters for scientific conferences). In fact, the main communication tools will be periodically complemented with new materials reporting the updates on the project. Press releases and magazine journals will be published periodically to communicate the main project achievements and emerging innovation.

8.1 Visual identity (completed)

The visual identity characterizes all the DIS-COM activities. It comprises the logo, imagery, typography, colors, and creative design that characterize the FRESH project with a distinguishable brand. The visual identity captures and conveys the symbolic meaning of the project and its targeted technology, while expressing its ambitions, content and characteristics. The visual identity has been used for designing the project's website, social media pages and dissemination materials. It is the branding for the FRESH project.

Figure 2. FRESH Logo and visual identity

8.2 Project website (completed)

The website design of the FRESH project has been finalized at M6 by the CNR. The website will be updated on a monthly basis with content collected from the partners. The uploaded content will be synergic to the content published on social media. The website will tell “the FRESH story” through a storytelling approach that will be developed during the project.

FRESH Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan D7.2

Figure 3. Website

8.3 Communication materials

Communication materials including brochures, posters and a roll-up will be prepared. The materials will be used in all communication activities to promote the FRESH project. The materials will be updated in the second half of the project with relevant results, focusing on the start-ups and SMEs' group of stakeholders.

8.4 Video

At M15, the FRESH's project video will be released to increase the engagement of the targeted stakeholder groups. The video has been designed in graphic motion to explain the innovativeness of the FRESH's prototype. The video will be "break-up" in five small video-pills to share on social media.

8.5 Press releases

Press releases will be organized to communicate key project achievements. The main press release is expected at the end of the project (M36) when the project's results will be presented at the final dissemination event.

8.6 Articles on magazines and non-scientific journals

Articles on sectorial magazines and non-scientific journals will be written to periodically communicate the FRESH project to professional communities and to generic audiences. Among the targeted magazines, there are the partner's magazines and the dissemination magazines of the EC (e.g Research*EU Magazines). Other magazines include online journals and blogs in the energy and hydrogen sectors as well as local newspapers.

8.7 Social Media (completed)

Social media are very effective in attracting the interest of the multiple stakeholders and in actively participating to the latest discussion on energy policies. The FRESH project has activated three social media channels:

- A LinkedIn page of the Project ----- achieve wide EU citizens stakeholders
- A Twitter profile of the Project ---- achieve political and industrial stakeholder.
- An Instagram profile of the Project to reach a wider audience.

The LinkedIn page and Twitter profile will be managed by the CNR. Partners are invited to follow the FRESH profiles on social media and re-post the tweets/posts on their institutional or personal profiles.

8.8 Other Media

Other media channels (videos, TV/Radio Interview, Newspapers, Podcasts, Blogs, etc.) might be used to communicate the FRESH project. Each action will be reported in the updated version of this deliverable.

9. Dissemination Plan

Figure 4. Dissemination Plan

The dissemination plan complements and connects to the communication plan. The following sections provide the main dissemination activities identified for the FRESH project. Whereas the starting of the communication activities is scheduled for the beginning of the project, dissemination activities will begin mostly after M12. Given that dissemination consists in sharing research results with potential users (peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers), one year is the minimum time necessary to collect, analyze and publish relevant results. The dissemination activities are clustered in five types: scientific publications, international conference and workshops, educational activities, exploitation workshops and final dissemination event. Details on each type of activities are provided in the next sections.

9.1 Educational activities

The FRESH research partners plan to organize courses and seminars on the main topics of the project, targeting PhDs, university students and high-school students. The purpose of educational activities is to raise interest among students in water electrolysis technologies and to provide a concrete example of applied research in the hydrogen production and energy sector. Table 2 reports the educational activities planned by the Consortium partners and the estimated number of engages stakeholders.

Table 2. List of undertaken and planned educational activities

Partner	Date	Type of educational activity	Title	Target audience	Tool used	Links
CNR	2022-2025	Bachelor, Masters and PhD thesis	TBD	Students	Thesis	https://www.unisi.it/ricerca/dottorati-di-ricerca-0
DTU	2023-2025	PhD Thesis	TBD	Student	Thesis	https://www.cere.dtu.dk/research-and-projects
FZJ	2023	Masters thesis	TBD	Student	Thesis	https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/iek/iek-14

9.2 Scientific publications

Scientific publications represent one of the most important dissemination tools to share research results in the scientific communities and contribute to advance science in general. The FRESH consortium targets international scientific communities in the fields of Carbon Capture and Storage, electrolysers, Fuel cells and electrocatalysis and energy storage technologies. In order to contribute to advance the state of the art in these fields, the FRESH consortium aims at presenting and publishing key scientific results emerging from the project in international scientific journals. Table 3 presents the list of published and foreseen scientific publications, the working papers and the conference proceedings published by the consortium partners. The table will be updated during the project periodic reporting.

Table 3. List of published and planned scientific publications

Date	Type	Title	Journal	Doi	Partners
2023 (planned)	Scientific publication	Electrocatalysis with formate in alkaline fuel cells	Peer-reviewed Journal		CNR

9.3 International conferences and workshops

In order to present the research results to the targeted scientific communities, the FRESH partners will attend international scientific conferences and workshops. The main goal of this activity will be to disseminate the project results, obtain feedback on the presented results and identify potential opportunities for collaboration with other researchers and stakeholders operating in the targeted field. Table 4 presents the

list of international conferences, external seminars and workshops attended by the Consortium from M1 to M12 and the planned activities for the second project year.

Table 4. List of planned international conferences, external seminars and workshops

Date	Type of event	Title	Target audience	Tool used	Links	Partners
May 30 – June 03 2022	IFAT Munich 2022	Research and innovation projects Filling the gap between research and industry Hysytech Srl, R&D department	Industry	Poster and Stand	https://ifat.de/en/	HySytech
26-28 Oct 2022	Conferenza di Dipartimento DSCTM-CNR	Electrocatalysts for future sustainable energy generation and storage	Scientific community	Presentation	https://www.dsctm.cnr.it/it/archivio-m/eventi-m.html	CNR
13-17 February 2023	ENERCHEM SCHOOL	Co-deposited nickel phases with tartaric acid as anodic electrodes	Students	Poster	http://www.enerchem-school.it/	CNR
03-08 Sept 2023	Presentation at 74 th Annual Meeting of the International Society of Electrochemistry	Developing Sustainable Electrocatalysts for Hydrogen Oxidation and Hydrogen Evolution in Anion Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells and Electrolyzers.	Scientific community	Presentation	https://annual74.ise-online.org/	CNR
08-12 Oct 2023	Presentation at 244 th ECS Meeting	Developing Sustainable Electrocatalysts for Hydrogen Oxidation and Hydrogen Evolution in	Scientific community	Presentation	https://www.electrochem.org/244	CNR

		Anion Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells and Electrolyzers.				
05-09 June 2023	EUBCE 2023 31st European Biomass Conference and Exhibition	TBD	Scientific and industrial community	TBD	https://www.eubce.com/	DTU

9.4 Exploitation workshops

Two stakeholder workshops will be organized in the third and last year of the project to disseminate the results of the FRESH project to interested stakeholders (D7.5). The final workshop will be linked to a bigger related event that year (e.g. a conference on CCU, carbon-neutral fuels, renewable energies or climate change).

10. Conclusions

This document presented the Dissemination and Communication Plan for the FRESH project. Following the definition and agreement of common communication principles, the document presents in detail the activities that will be undertaken by the Consortium during the three years of project. This document is strictly related to the *Deliverable D7.2 – Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan*. The dissemination and communication activities will be performed with the main objectives of supporting the engagement of the identified stakeholder groups that can be interested in exploiting the FRESH results.

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